

LAMP-based electrochemical platform for monitoring HPV genome integration at the mRNA level associated with higher risk of cervical cancer progression

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Abstract

Human papillomaviruses (HPVs) represent a diverse group of double-stranded DNA viruses associated with various types of cancers, notably cervical cancer. High-risk types of HPVs exhibit their oncogenic potential through the integration of their DNA into the host genome. This integration event contributes significantly to genomic instability and the progression of malignancy. However, traditional detection methods, such as immunohistochemistry or PCR-based assays, face inherent challenges, and thus alternative tools are being developed to fasten and simplify the analysis. Our study introduces an innovative biosensing platform that combines loop-mediated amplification with electrochemical (EC) analysis for the specific detection of HPV16 integration. By targeting key elements like the E7 mRNA, a central player in HPV integration, and the E2 viral gene transcript lost upon integration, we show clear distinction between episomal and integrated forms of HPV16. Our EC data confirmed higher E7 expression in HPV16-positive cell lines having integrated forms of viral genome, while E2 expression was diminished in cells with fully integrated genomes. Moreover, we revealed distinct expression patterns in cervical tissue of patients, correlating well with digital droplet PCR, qRT-PCR, or immunohistochemical staining. Our platform thus offers insights into HPV integration in clinical samples and facilitates further advancements in cervical cancer research and diagnostics.

KEYWORDS

cervical cancer, electrochemistry, HPV integration, human papillomavirus, RT-LAMP

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1 | INTRODUCTION

The human papillomavirus (HPV, *Papillomaviridae* family, *Alphapapillomavirus* genus) is a double-stranded DNA virus associated with epithelial tissue infections and various types of cancers, especially cervical cancer. This is particularly due to the integration of high-risk HPV types, especially HPV16 and HPV18, into the host genome. Persistent infection with high-risk HPV types is a critical etiological factor in the development and progression of high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions (HSIL), emphasizing the importance of HPV screening. It is important to note that while HSIL is closely linked to precancerous lesions, not all cases progress to cancer. However, it is regarded as a critical precursor to malignancy and warrants serious clinical attention.¹ In contrast, low-grade squamous epithelial lesions (LSILs) typically represent transient HPV infections that spontaneously regress within two to 5 years and carry a low risk of progressing to cancer.^{2,3}

Although specific integration sites are not well-defined, HPV integration tends to occur near common fragile sites within the genome,⁴ that is, regions naturally prone to genomic instability. This phenomenon has been observed in more than half of HPV16-positive cancers and most HPV18-positive malignancies, suggesting that integration may, in certain cases, contribute to the progression towards malignancy.⁵ In episomal HPV genomes, the E2 protein directly suppresses expression of early E6 and E7 genes, regulating HPV copy number⁶ and thus acting as a replication factor.⁷ Integration of viral DNA negatively affects the E2 expression, leading to uncontrolled E6 and E7 expression.^{4,8,9} This is considered a critical step in the progression to cancer by disrupting key cellular processes associated with cell cycle control or DNA mismatch repair,^{5,10} in which E6 and E7 proteins serve as inhibitors of tumor suppressor proteins p53 and Rb (retinoblastoma protein), respectively.^{4,11} E6 and E7 mRNAs expressed from integrated copies of HPV show an increased stability, and integration confers a selective growth advantage over cells that only harbor episomal copies of viral DNA.^{12,13}

Early methods for HPV detection included immunohistochemistry (IHC)^{14,15} using monoclonal antibodies against p16, Ki-67 or HPV L1 proteins, and fluorescent in situ hybridization⁴ utilizing DNA probes for HPV sequences. Later, PCR-based methods became a gold standard for HPV analysis.^{16–18} Various PCR protocols have been outlined, where the inability to amplify specific targets within the E1 or E2 ORFs may suggest viral integration.^{19–21} However, methods for analyzing HPV integration into the host genome are not so common due to more complicated workflows. They mostly assess integration by quantifying relative expression of E2/E7,^{4,12,22–24} by identifying Alu repetitive sequences,⁴ or by involving ligation-mediated PCR to distinguish between integrated and episomal forms based on differences in amplicon size.¹⁶ The advent of next-generation sequencing of both RNA and DNA has allowed precise determination of the sites of integration and the genomic rearrangements at integration loci.^{25–27} However, these methods also face various limitations, especially high cost due to the need for specialized equipment and reagents. Moreover, they are often time-consuming, requiring careful sample preparation and analysis, and demand a high level of expertise from the operator to ensure accuracy and reliable results. PCR, in addition, requires temperature

cycling using thermal cyclers, and is sensitive to various inhibitors. These limitations have prompted the development and adoption of more efficient and cost-effective techniques in recent years.

Isothermal amplification techniques (IATs) could replace PCR-based methods by providing shorter amplification times, moderate constant temperatures without the need for thermal cycling, and better resistance to PCR inhibitors.²⁸ Perhaps the most common IAT is a loop-mediated amplification (LAMP), operating between 60°C and 70°C.²⁹ LAMP is extremely sensitive (due to its exponential amplification similar to PCR), specific (4–6 primers are required) and tolerant to various PCR inhibitors and has been widely used for detection of HPV. Recently, electrochemical (EC) techniques have emerged as interesting detection platforms, offering fast detection times, relatively inexpensive and simple instrumentation, and the possibility of parallel detection on miniaturized electrode chips.^{28,30,31} These features make EC techniques ideal for personalized medicine and point-of-care diagnostics.³² In this context, we have published several research articles reporting fast and simple LAMP-based assays combined with EC detection, targeting HPV16/18 genotypes in both cervical cell lines and cervical swab samples from women with precancerous lesions.^{33–36} These works have proven that EC detection connected to LAMP may be a powerful tool to quickly analyze HPV presence by detecting viral DNA, but until now, we have not focused on analysis of HPV mRNAs.

In this study, we aimed for the first time to explore a novel approach for detecting integration of HPV16 by developing an RNA-based biosensing platform combining LAMP in a reverse transcription mode (RT-LAMP) and EC analysis in a rapid and simple way. Indeed, novel diagnostic tests that could differentiate between episomal and integrated forms of HPV infection could provide critical insights into the lesion's potential to progress. Our platform, which we refer to as eRT-LAMP, focuses on EC detection of two viral mRNAs, that is, E2 and E7. The E2 is expressed at normal levels, maintaining control over E7 and thereby preventing excessive cell proliferation. However, when the virus integrates into the host genome, the E2 gene is often disrupted or deleted at the integration site, leading to a loss of its regulatory function. This results in uncontrolled expression of E7, driving the host cells towards a malignant phenotype. Therefore, the ratio of E2 to E7 expression serves as a critical biomarker for determining the state of HPV16 infection. Here, we calculated E2/E7 ratio that confirmed integration status of HPV16 not only in cervical cancer cell lines, but was also used to predict the HPV integration status in 18 cervical samples. Our bioplatfrom was validated by standard techniques, including classical PCR with gel electrophoresis, digital PCR at both mRNA and DNA level, as well as by analysis of p16 status by IHC staining, showing good correlation with all techniques. The bioplatfrom thus offers a simple alternative to quickly determine HPV integration status as an indicator of disease progression.

2 | EXPERIMENTAL

List of material and apparatus, oligonucleotide sequences (Supporting Information S1: Table 1), complete protocols for droplet digital PCR, qRT-PCR (Supporting Information S1: Table 2) and IHC, as well as

data analysis section can be found in Supporting Information, along with a general scheme of p16 analysis (Supporting Information S1: Figure 1).

2.1 | Cell lines

Cervical carcinoma cell lines CaSki and SiHa (HPV16-positive) were cultured in Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 Medium. HeLa, a cervical cancer cell line (HPV18-positive) was cultured in dulbecco's modified eagle medium (DMEM), and C4-I (also HPV18-positive) was cultured in McCoy's media. HPV-negative cell lines included colorectal cancer cell lines SW620 and HT-29, both cultured in DMEM, and prostate adenocarcinoma cell line Lymph Node Carcinoma of the Prostate (LNCaP) and ovarian cancer cell line A2780, both cultured in RPMI. All culture media were supplemented with 1% L-glutamine (for RPMI), 1% pyruvate (for DMEM), 1× penicillin-streptomycin (Biosera), and 10% Fetal Bovine Serum from Gibco. All cell lines were incubated at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂. For RNA extraction, Total RNA Purification kit was used; for DNA extraction, the Tissue DNA Preparation Column Kit was used (both Jena Bioscience).

2.2 | Clinical samples

The study received ethical approval from the Ethical Committee of the University Hospital in Brno, and informed consent was obtained from all patients. Cervical samples were collected directly into homogenization buffer (0.4 M ammonium thiocyanate, 0.8 M guanidine thiocyanate, 0.1 M sodium acetate, 5% glycerol, and 38% phenol) and stored at -80°C until further analysis. DNA and RNA from cervical samples was extracted with the chloroform-based DNA and RNA extraction according to the protocol (see Supporting Information). The concentration of DNA and RNA was measured spectrophotometrically at 260 nm using NanoDrop 1000 (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

2.3 | LAMP reaction

After RNA extraction, 500 ng of total RNA was treated with 2 µL of 10× diluted DNase I according to the manufacturer's protocol, into a final volume of 15 µL. Then, 5 µL of the treated RNA was used for LAMP reaction, with a total RNA input of 166 ng. The reaction mixture contained 5 µL of 2× Warm Start LAMP Master Mix, 0.5 µL of F3/B3 primer mix (original concentration of 5 µM), 0.5 µL of FIP/BIP primer mix (original concentration of 40 µM) and 0.3 µL of 1 mM digoxigenin-modified dUTP nucleotides. For HPV16 E7 target, the reaction was incubated at 64°C for 70 min. For HPV16 E2 target, the same protocol was followed, with the addition of 0.5 µL loop primer mix (with an original concentration of 10 µM). The reaction was then incubated at 67°C for 20 min.

2.4 | Hybridization on magnetic beads (MBs)

Two microliters of MBs were washed three times with a washing buffer (WB, 1 M NaCl, 0.5 mM EDTA, and 5 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.6) and incubated with 1.2 µM solution of biotinylated capture probe (CP) designed for HPV16 E7, HPV16 E2 or 18S rRNA (Supporting Information S1: Table 1) for 15 min at room temperature (RT). MBs were then washed three times with 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 6.0 (PB) and incubated with 4 µL of DIG-labeled LAMP products in PB, allowing them to hybridize to the capture probe for 15 min at RT. After 3 more MB washing with blocking buffer (BB, Blocker Casein in PBS with 1% BSA), the final incubation step with antiDIG-horseradish peroxidase (HRP) (diluted at a ratio of 1:1000 in BB) was introduced for 15 min at RT. All incubation steps were on a rotator with gentle rotation. Finally, the MBs were washed three times with PB and resuspended in a total volume of 10 µL of PB.

2.5 | EC measurements

The 10 µL of resuspended MBs were applied onto the working carbon screen-printed electrode surface, with the magnetic support positioned below. All three electrodes were covered with 50 µL solution of PB containing 10 mM hydroquinone and 50 mM hydrogen peroxide, serving as a substrate for HRP. Amperometry was carried out at -0.3 V for a duration of 60 s to monitor the electric current generated from the enzymatic reaction. A photograph of this setup is shown in Supporting Information S1: Figure 2.

2.6 | Exo V treatment

Reaction mixture for digestion comprised 1× NEBuffer 4, 1 mM ATP, 5 units of Exo V and 400 ng of DNA extracted from the cell lines, in a total volume of 10 µL. Digestion was conducted at 37°C for 45 min, followed by an Exo V inactivation by adding 50 mM EDTA, pH 8, at 70°C for 30 min. Digested DNA samples were analyzed by digital droplet PCR (ddPCR).

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Assay principles

Our goal was to develop a model system targeting E7 mRNA involved in the integration of the virus into the host genome. We chose E7 instead of E6 mRNA, since full-length E6 transcripts in HPV-associated cervical lesions were shown to be relatively scarce, while E7 transcripts were highly represented in terms of absolute number and relative abundance in clinical samples.³⁷ In parallel, we have also targeted a transcript of E2 viral gene that is usually lost during integration. Throughout the whole study, we have selected HPV16 as the most frequent oncogenic genotype of HPV.³⁸ Figure 1 shows a

FIGURE 1 Assay workflow, comprising RNA extraction from cervical cells/cervical tissue followed by RT-LAMP amplification of HPV16 E7 and E2 mRNAs, hybridization of LAMP products at the surface of streptavidin magnetic beads and EC measurement of captured LAMP products via enzymatic reaction at carbon electrode chips. EC, electrochemical; LAMP, loop-mediated amplification; RT-LAMP, reverse transcription.

simplified workflow of our assay. After extraction of total RNA from these cell lines, RNA samples were amplified using a single-step RT-LAMP to produce DNA product. The LAMP mixture contained digoxigenin-labeled dUTPs, randomly incorporated alongside dTTPs. These labeled products were mixed with streptavidin magnetic beads coated with biotinylated capture probes. After hybridization, anti-digoxigenin antibodies conjugated to HRP facilitated the final amperometric readout of the enzymatic reaction. Measurements were carried out on eight-electrode array, greatly decreasing overall time by simultaneously interrogating eight samples instead of measuring one by one as in most conventional assays. To increase the signal, a magnet was placed beneath the electrode array during the measurement that attracted magnetic beads to the electrode surface for pre-concentration of HRP molecules. The assay required optimization of various parameters; these parameters (including tested values and selected ones) are found in Supporting Information S1: Table 3, and corresponding experimental data are available in Supporting Information S1: Figures 3–8.

3.2 | mRNA detection using panel of cell lines

To construct the model RNA bioassay, a panel of cell lines with known HPV16 integration status was used, comprising cervical cancer cell lines CaSki (with integrated and extrachromosomal HPV16), SiHa (with fully integrated HPV16), HeLa and C4-I (negative for HPV16, but positive for HPV18), as well as noncervical cancer cell lines negative for any HPV types (HT-29, SW620, A2780, LNCaP). EC signals at the mRNA level obtained from this panel clearly showed high E7 expression for CaSki and SiHa, and the absence of E7 mRNA in the rest of the cell lines without any HPV16 (Figure 2A). On the contrary, EC signal for E2 mRNA completely disappeared in SiHa (where HPV is fully integrated into the host genome), while a

relatively high EC signal (and thus active expression) of E2 was observed in CaSki cell lines (although still lower than E7 expression). This is in agreement with a recent study reporting an induction of interchromosomal translocations and the formation of extra-chromosomal circular virus-human hybrid structures (ECC) in CaSki, but not in SiHa cell line.³⁹ Similarly to E7 mRNA, no signals were obtained for HPV16-negative cell lines using E2 primers. These findings are consistent with the expected expression patterns of CaSki and SiHa cell lines reported in the literature.^{8,11} Moreover, we also added DNA controls to show functionality of primers, that is, targeting E7 and E2 genes from CaSki DNA (since viral DNA contains both of these genes and have the same sequence as mRNAs). Raw amperometric curves of all these samples are visible in Supporting Information S1: Figure 9. In addition to E7 and E2, we assessed EC signals from 18S rRNA, a widely recognized housekeeping gene known for its consistent expression across various tissues and cells, to confirm the sample quality (Supporting Information S1: Figure 10a). Strong EC signals of similar intensities across all cell lines demonstrate suitability of 18S rRNA as a reliable internal control, as confirmed by a gel electrophoresis that displayed typical ladder-like patterns of LAMP products. Supporting Information S1: Figure 11 shows E7 and E2 signals that were normalized to 18S rRNA signals, that is, E7/18S rRNA and E2/18S rRNA ratios. The results are qualitatively similar to the not normalized ones, but the normalized values better reflect quality of the samples and take into account expression profiles that can differ among individual cell lines.⁴⁰ To verify our results, we compared data from our eRT-LAMP with two standard techniques, digital droplet PCR (ddPCR, Figure 2B and Supporting Information S1: Figure 10b) and quantitative reverse transcription PCR (RT-qPCR, Supporting Information S1: Figure 12). Both validation techniques were performed on the same panel of cell lines, showing similar results as with eRT-LAMP, that is, higher expression of E7 in CaSki and SiHa, lower but apparent expression of E2 only in

FIGURE 2 (A) The bar graph showing electrochemical signals of the RT-LAMP assay using HPV16 E7 LAMP (blue) and HPV16 E2 primers (pink) on a panel of total RNA from various cell lines. (B) The bar graph showing concentration (copies/ μL) of the positive droplet of PCR product using HPV16 E7 (blue) and HPV16 E2 PCR primers (pink) on a panel of cDNA from various cell lines. EC, electrochemical; LAMP, loop-mediated amplification; RT-LAMP, reverse transcription.

FIGURE 3 (A) The scheme of exonuclease V treatment of genomic DNA. (B) Concentration (copies/ μL) of positive droplets for E7 before (blue) and after the treatment (orange) in selected cell lines, and comparison with the classical PCR with gel electrophoresis (using same primers and cell lines, inset).

CaSki, and negligible expression for the rest. These results thus confirm the reliability of our model and provide a solid starting point for evaluating HPV integration in clinical samples. Moreover, we have tested analytical sensitivity of our assay (concentration dependence, Supporting Information S1: Figure 13) as well as repeatability from 6 independent measurements for three different RNA inputs (10, 50, and 100 ng; Supporting Information S1: Table 4).

3.3 | Exonuclease treatment of viral DNA

To further verify the integration of HPV into the DNA of selected cell lines, we applied a protocol involving digestion of DNA with an Exo V and amplification of treated DNA with PCR E7 primers (Figure 3A). The Exo V enzyme specifically cleaves linear DNA in both directions, leaving the circular DNA intact,⁴¹ and is often used for degradation of contaminating linear DNA in plasmid samples. Absolute quantification

using ddPCR was monitored before and after the treatment; presence of positive droplets before the treatment indicated HPV16 presence in DNA samples, regardless of an integration status. On the other hand, evaluation of droplets after the treatment was used to assess linearity of DNA, where negative droplets indicated presence of linear DNA and thus fully integrated HPV, while positive droplets suggested presence of circular DNA in either episomal or secondary excised circular DNA.

Consistent with our previous findings for E7 mRNA, the ddPCR results at the DNA level revealed that CaSki and SiHa exhibited high number of positive droplets before the Exo V treatment, suggesting the presence of HPV16 DNA (Figure 3B and Supporting Information S1: Figure 14). After the treatment, CaSki positive droplet numbers significantly dropped but did not disappear, suggesting presence of both integrated and ECC DNA, while SiHa showed no positive droplets after the Exo V treatment, confirming the complete integration of HPV16 into its host genome. These observations provide

TABLE 1 Analysis of 18 clinical samples using Cobas, IHC, ddPCR, and our eRT-LAMP technique, along with a concordance of eRT-RNA with other methods.

#	Histology	HPV type (Cobas)	p16	eRT-LAMP		ddPCR (RNA)		ddPCR (DNA)		Agreement		
				E2/E7	Integ.	E2/E7	Integ.	E7 ratio	Integ.	IHC	ddPCR (RNA)	ddPCR (DNA)
1	AC	16	+	0.05	+	0.00	+	0.01	+	Y/N	Y/N	Y/N
2	AC	16	+	0.01	+	0.01	+	0.04	+	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	HSIL	16	+	0.04	+	0.18	+	0.04	+	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	HSIL	16	F+	0.80	+	0.05	+	0.14	+	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	HSIL	16	+	0.00	+	0.06	+	0.34	+	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	HSIL	16	+	0.02	+	0.85	+	0.00	+	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	HSIL	16	+	0.02	+	0.55	+	0.05	+	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	HSIL	16	+	0.00	+	0.56	+	0.38	+	Yes	Yes	Yes
9	LSIL	16	-	3.35	-	3.81	-	1.43	-	Yes	Yes	Yes
10	LSIL	16	-	Negative	IC	Negative	IC	Negative	IC	N/A	Yes	Yes
11	LSIL	16	-	1.35	-	1.42	-	1.05	+	Yes	Yes	No
12	LSIL	16	F+	0.00	+	0.44	+	0.00	+	Yes	Yes	Yes
13	LSIL	16	-	0.00	+	1.08	-	0.00	+	No	No	Yes
14	LSIL	16	-	2.20	-	5.18	-	1.06	-	Yes	Yes	Yes
15	HSIL	18	+	Negative	---	Negative	---	Negative	---	N/A	Yes	Yes
16	Negative	0	-	Negative	---	Negative	---	Negative	---	Yes	Yes	Yes
17	Negative	0	-	Negative	---	Negative	---	Negative	---	Yes	Yes	Yes
18	Negative	0	-	Negative	---	Negative	---	Negative	---	Yes	Yes	Yes

Abbreviations: AC, adenocarcinoma; ddPCR, digital droplet PCR; F+, focal positivity; IHC, immunohistochemistry; integ, integration status, where “+” indicates integrated form and “-” episomal form; inc: inconclusive; LAMP, loop-mediated amplification; RT-LAMP, reverse transcription.

further evidence supporting the fully integrated HPV16 status in SiHa and the presence of extrachromosomal HPV in CaSki, as reported in the literature.³⁹

To confirm our ddPCR results obtained with the DNA-based platform, we performed PCR reaction with the final gel electrophoresis readout on the same set of samples. Figure 3B shows the gel, where a loss of SiHa DNA after the treatment is apparent; CaSki DNA, on the other hand, was protected from complete degradation, showing correlation of both methods and also good agreement with the literature.³⁹

3.4 | Application to clinical samples

As a proof of concept, we have applied the proposed method to clinical material, that is, total RNA extracted from HPV16-induced LSILs and HSILs samples, as well as negative controls without HPV infection (Supporting Information S1: Table 5). We have included total of 18 clinical samples with various HPV status (as confirmed by Cobas testing, Table 1), focusing predominantly on HPV16 genotype. Of those 18 samples, 14 were HPV16-positive (samples 1–14), 1 was HPV18-positive (sample 15) and 3 were HPV negative (samples

16–18). HPV16-positive samples were further classified as 2 adenocarcinomas (samples 1–2), 6 HSILs (samples 3–8), and 6 LSILs (samples 9–14).

First, we tested the clinical samples with standard methods, that is, ddPCR and p16 staining. The ddPCR analysis on 18 samples was performed both at the RNA and DNA level. On the RNA level, we assessed the expression levels of E2 and E7 (Figure 4A). Our findings indicated that out of the 14 HPV16-positive samples, 9 of them exhibited signs of integration, while four appeared to be non-integrated. Notably, sample 10 showed negative results for both the E7 and E2 regions, suggesting a lack of HPV presence or low viral load in this particular sample. At the DNA level, each DNA sample was divided into two aliquots. One aliquot underwent Exo V treatment, while the other remained untreated, and absolute levels of the E7 gene were then quantified by ddPCR (Figure 4B). Ten samples showed evidence of integration and three samples appeared non-integrated. The sample 10, similarly to the mRNA results, was tested negative for the E7 gene, suggesting the lack of HPV.

The second validation technique, the IHC analysis of overexpressed p16 protein in premalignant and malignant lesions, is a useful indicator of cervical cancer progression. It was shown that the p16 positivity increases with increasing grades of dysplasia, thus helping to stratify

FIGURE 4 (A) The bar graph showing concentration (copies/ μL) of the positive droplet of PCR product using HPV16 E7 (blue) and HPV16 E2 PCR primers (pink) on cDNA from clinical samples. (B) The bar graph showing concentration (copies/ μL) of the positive droplet of PCR product using HPV16 E7 before exonuclease treatment (blue) and HPV16 E7 after exonuclease treatment (orange) on DNA from clinical samples.

neoplastic lesions.⁴² All samples were tested for p16 positivity (Table 1), indicating that all 8 samples classified as HSIL tested positive for p16. Among LSIL samples, five were negative for p16, while one LSIL sample exhibited focal positivity, indicating a mosaic pattern of p16 expression. This mosaic pattern suggests the presence of both p16-positive and p16-negative cells within the sample.

Then, using the same clinical samples, we have performed EC analysis of both E7 and E2 mRNAs (Figure 5D). Samples that were negative for HPV16 (samples 15–18) provided only negligible signals for both E2 and E7. Regarding HPV16-positive samples, we have calculated their E2/E7 ratios, as suggested by a study Park et al.⁴⁰ where they examined the ratio of integrated to episomal forms of HPV DNA by quantifying HPV16 E6 RNA relative to E2 DNA, as the E2 gene is frequently lost during integration. They suggested that E2/E6 ratio > 1 indicated a predominance of episomal virus forms, while a lower E2/E6 ratio < 0.5 suggested a predominance of integrated virus forms. We have performed an ROC analysis to identify the best threshold, yielding AUC of 0.75 and threshold value of ~ 1.1 (Supporting Information S1: Figure 15, inset), that is, similar as in the above-mentioned study. Based on this, our samples with E2/E7 ratio of EC signals over 1.1 was considered to have an episomal HPV DNA (due to higher content of E2 mRNA than E7 mRNA), while ratio below 1.1 was considered to be partially or fully integrated. As shown in Table 1, three samples had ratio of E2/E7 > 1.1 , suggesting their

episomal character (samples 9, 11, and 14), 10 samples had ratio of E2/E7 < 1.1 and thus were considered integrated, and one sample (sample 10) was negative for both E2 and E7 (sample 10), and so the ratio could not be calculated (correlating with ddPCR results). Along E2 and E7 mRNAs, we have measured EC signals of 18S rRNA (after LAMP reaction) as an internal control to check quality of input RNA samples and that LAMP proceeded correctly (Figure 5D). The quality of an input material was sufficient since all samples were positive for 18S rRNA.

The scatter plots in Figure 5A–C display EC data with dots representing E2/E7 ratio of HPV16 for each HPV16-positive clinical sample (i.e., samples 1–14, except the sample 10). Again, dots < 1.1 (below dotted line) indicate viral integration and dots > 1.1 point to episomal form of the virus. In all three scatter plots, dots were separated into two groups based either on IHC results (p16-positive and p16-negative, Figure 5A), ddPCR results at the mRNA level (Figure 5B) and ddPCR at the DNA level (Figure 5C). For instance, when the biopsy sample was p16-positive, the DNA from a liquid cytology sample suggested possible integration, and vice versa. The Mann–Whitney tests for all scatter plots revealed significant (Figure 5A,B) or highly significant differences (Figure 5C).

Finally, we assessed our assay's performance against IHC and ddPCR. Our assay demonstrated 100% sensitivity, accurately identifying all infected individuals (see Supporting Information S1: Table 6

FIGURE 5 Analysis of a clinical material. Scatter plot showing EC values of E2/E7 ratio. Two and four stars denote significant and highly significant differences with p Values 0.004 (A), 0.004 (B) and 0.0001 (C). Division into groups was made based on IHC (A), RNA-ddPCR (B) and DNA-ddPCR (C) results. (D) The bar graph showing signals of the eRT-LAMP assay using HPV16 E7 LAMP (blue), HPV16 E2 primers (pink) and 18S rRNA (green) on total RNA from clinical samples. LAMP, loop-mediated amplification; RT-LAMP, reverse transcription.

for more details). Nonintegrated samples exhibited positive predictive values of 90% compared to IHC and ddPCR RNA and 100% compared to ddPCR DNA, while integrated samples showed a negative predictive value of 100% across all methods. This study thus extends the applicability and robustness of our EC-LAMP method for HPV detection and gene expression analysis from cell line models to real clinical samples.

4 | DISCUSSION

For the first time, we show here a simple and rapid EC-based bio-assay that may indicate integration status of the HPV and thus to assess a risk of progression of precancerous cervical lesions. Indeed, overall time of our eRT-LAMP is approx. 120 min, while ddPCR requires (for 18 samples/one gene) at least 270 min, suggesting > twofold time reduction. Our methodology is straightforward, yet highly sensitive and selective. We were able to detect E7 mRNA in as little as 6 ng of total RNA from CaSki cell line, harboring only one active copy of HPV (the rest being methylated). By offering reliable detection at such low RNA input levels and by detecting as few as one active transcript, our EC-based method holds promise for further advancing HPV research and clinical diagnostics.

As a validation technique, we have selected ddPCR as a highly sensitive variant of PCR, offering absolute quantification of nucleic acid template. Besides mRNA validation (Figure 4A), we have included ddPCR-based approach at the DNA level before and after Exo V treatment (Figure 4B). The rationale behind this experiment lies in the expected behavior of integrated and nonintegrated HPV DNA. Fully integrated HPV, as part of the host genome, would be not protected from Exo V degradation, resulting in no positive droplet after treatment. In contrast, nonintegrated DNA that exists in either secondary excised ECC or episomal forms, is not susceptible to the Exo V degradation and the signal is retained.

The Table 1 shows several discrepancies in clinical sample analysis, which occurred even among individual validation techniques. The IHC and ddPCR at the RNA level suggested nonintegration status of HPV16 in five and four samples, respectively, while indicating integration in nine samples for both methods. Conversely, our assay identified three samples as nonintegrated HPV16 and 10 samples as integrated HPV16 (and one sample was negative for E2 and E7). The agreement between our method and ddPCR, or between our method and IHC was the same (94%, 16/17 samples). Perfect agreement was reached when comparing our method with ddPCR at the DNA level (100%, 17/17 samples). It should be noted that sample 10 was negative for both E2 and E7 mRNA using not only our method, but also using ddPCR at both RNA and DNA level. On the

other hand, sample 10 was tested positive for HPV16 using Cobas methodology. This could be due to a time delay between sample collection, preparation and processing. An exfoliative cytology (collected with the brush) as well the punch biopsy from the expert colposcopy was performed during the first visit at the gynecologist. Cytological sample was used for Cobas analysis to identify HPV, while the biopsy sample was used in histopathological diagnostics, including p16 analysis. At the second visit involving conization (usually after several months), another cervical brush was taken, and the extracted nucleic acid was used for eRT-LAMP and ddPCR analysis (at both RNA and DNA level). It is thus not excluded that HPV infection could be cleared (the sample was considered as LSIL). We are aware that the clinical sample size is relatively low due to limited number of samples that had a complete analysis with all the validation techniques (Cobas, IHC, and ddPCR). On the other hand, this study is only a proof-of-concept to demonstrate feasibility of the assay, and a clinical study with larger number of samples should follow.

To conclude, the isothermal LAMP method rapidly amplifies nucleic acids without the need for a thermal cycler, making it a quick and highly sensitive alternative to PCR. Pairing it with EC detection provides an affordable and compact equipment, enabling parallel measurements on electrode chips. This setup could prove valuable for HPV analysis in an easy and rapid manner, for example, in decentralized medical settings, meeting the needs of point-of-care diagnostics.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Nasim Izadi prepared samples, carried out experiments and optimization at the mRNA level, performed validation techniques, and wrote some parts of the manuscript; Johana Strmiskova prepared samples and performed electrochemical measurements; Milan Anton collected cervical samples and edited the manuscript; Jitka Hausnerova performed IHC experiments; Martin Bartosik designed the concept, coordinated experimental part and wrote and edited the final version of the manuscript.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

ETHICS STATEMENT

The study received ethical approval from the Ethical Committee of the University Hospital in Brno, and informed consent was obtained from all patients. All experiments were performed in compliance with

relevant laws and institutional guidelines and in accordance with the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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